

Supplementary Figures



Supplementary Figure S1: *Abisaadichthys libanicus*, holotype, FSL-573086, scale bar: 1 cm.



Supplementary Figure S2: *Abisaadichthys libanicus*, holotype, FSL-573086, caudal region showing straight segmentation of the visible caudal fin rays, scale bar: 1 cm.



Supplementary Figure S3: *Protobama avus*, additional material, FSL-573081, scale bar: 1cm.



Supplementary Figure S4: *Protobama avus*, additional material, FSL-573082 a (A), b (B), scale bar: 2 cm.



Supplementary Figure S5: *Protobrama woodwardi*, (A) holotype, FSL-573084, and (B) paratype, FSL-573085, scale bar: 2 cm.



Supplementary Figure S6: *Eusebichthys byblosi*, holotype, MNHN-HAK-306, scale bar: 2 cm.



Supplementary Figure S7: *Eusebichthys byblosi*, holotype, MNHN-HAK-306, skull region, scale bar: 1 cm.